

Accurate Estimation of Areas Using the Mean of Lower and Upper Riemann Sums

Summary

This paper presents a new formula for estimating the area under the curve of a continuous function, based on Riemann sums. The proposed formula uses the average of the lower and upper Riemann sums to obtain a more accurate estimate of the area. Practical examples are provided to demonstrate the effectiveness and accuracy of the approach.

Introduction

Integration is a key tool in the calculation to determine the area under a curve. Traditional methods, such as Riemann sums, offer ways to approximate this area. However, these approximations may have precision limitations depending on the number of subintervals used. This paper proposes a new approach that uses the mean of the lower and upper Riemann sums to improve the accuracy of area estimation.

Methodology

Somas de Riemann

For a function $f(x)$ defined in an interval $[a, b]$, Riemann sums are calculated by dividing the interval into n subintervals wide $\Delta x = \frac{b-a}{n}$. The lower Riemann sum (L_n) and the upper Riemann sum (U_n) are defined as:

$$L_n = \sum_{i=1}^n f(m_i) \Delta x$$

$$U_n = \sum_{i=1}^n f(M_i) \Delta x$$

where m_i and M_i are the minimum and maximum points of $f(x)$ in the i -th subinterval, respectively.

New Approach: Mean Riemann Sums

The new formula proposes that the area A under the curve can be estimated by averaging the lower and upper Riemann sums:

$$A \approx \frac{1}{2} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n f(m_i) \Delta x + \sum_{i=1}^n f(M_i) \Delta x \right)$$

$$A \approx \frac{\Delta x}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n (f(m_i) + f(M_i))$$

Two-Dimensional Area Estimation

For two-variable functions, the same approach can be extended using double sums. Suppose we have a function $f(x, y)$ defined in a rectangular region $[a, b] \times [c, d]$. We divide this region into n subintervals along the x axis and m subintervals along the y axis, with $\Delta x = \frac{b-a}{n}$ and $\Delta y = \frac{d-c}{m}$.

The area A under the surface can be estimated by averaging the lower and upper Riemann sums:

$$L_{n,m} = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m f(m_{i,j}) \Delta x \Delta y$$

$$U_{n,m} = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m f(M_{i,j}) \Delta x \Delta y$$

where $m_{i,j}$ and $M_{i,j}$ are the minimum and maximum points of $f(x, y)$ in the (i, j) -th subrectangle, respectively.

The area (A) under the surface is then estimated by:

$$A \approx \frac{1}{2} (L_{n,m} + U_{n,m})$$

$$A \approx \frac{\Delta x \Delta y}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m (f(m_{i,j}) + f(M_{i,j}))$$

Examples and Results

Example 1: Quadratic Function $(f(x) = x^2)$

We consider the function $(f(x) = x^2)$ in the interval $([0, 1])$ and calculate the area using the new approach with $(n = 4)$ subintervals.

1. We divide the interval $([0, 1])$ into 4 subintervals of width $(\Delta x = 0.25)$.

2. We calculate the bottom and top sums:

[

$$L_4 = (0^2 \cdot 0.25) + (0.25^2 \cdot 0.25) + (0.5^2 \cdot 0.25) + (0.75^2 \cdot 0.25) = 0.21875$$

]

[

$$U_4 = (0.25^2 \cdot 0.25) + (0.5^2 \cdot 0.25) + (0.75^2 \cdot 0.25) + (1^2 \cdot 0.25) = 0.46875$$

]

3. The average of the sums is:

[

$$A \approx \frac{L_4 + U_4}{2} = \frac{0.21875 + 0.46875}{2} = 0.34375$$

]

Comparing with the actual area obtained by the integration:

[

$$A_{\text{real}} = \int_0^1 x^2 \, dx = \frac{1}{3} \approx 0.3333$$

]

The difference between the estimate and the actual area is approximately 0.01045, indicating good accuracy.

Example 2: Increasing Accuracy

We repeat the calculation with $(n = 8)$ subintervals:

1. We divide the interval into 8 sub-intervals of width $(\Delta x = 0.125)$.

2. We calculate the bottom and top sums:

\[

$$L_8 = 0 + 0.001953125 + 0.0078125 + 0.017578125 + 0.03125 + 0.048828125 + 0.0703125 + 0.095703125 = 0.2734375$$

\]

\[

$$U_8 = 0.001953125 + 0.0078125 + 0.017578125 + 0.03125 + 0.048828125 + 0.0703125 + 0.095703125 + 0.125 = 0.3984375$$

\]

3. The average of the sums is:

$$A \approx \frac{L_8 + U_8}{2} = \frac{0.2734375 + 0.3984375}{2} = 0.3359375$$

The difference between the estimate and the actual area is now approximately 0.0026375, demonstrating an increase in accuracy with increasing number of subintervals.

Conclusion

The average of the lower and upper Riemann sums offers an effective and accurate approach to the estimation of areas under curves and surfaces. Precision can be adjusted by increasing the number of subintervals, making this method a robust alternative to traditional Riemann sums. Future research may explore the application of the formula in other types of mathematical functions and contexts.

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